

Reinforced model selection for resource efficient anomaly detection in edge clouds

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ABSTRACT

Web application services and networks encounter a broad range of security and performance anomalies, necessitating sophisticated detection strategies. However, performing anomaly detection in edge cloud environments, often constrained by limited resources, presents significant computational challenges and demands minimized detection time for real-time response. In this paper, we propose a model selection approach for resource efficient anomaly detection in edge clouds by leveraging an adapted Deep Q-Network (DQN) reinforcement learning technique. The primary objective is to minimize the computational resources required for accurate anomaly detection while achieving low latency and high detection accuracy. Through extensive experimental evaluation in our testbed setup over different representative scenarios, we demonstrate that our adapted DQN approach can reduce resource usage by up to 45% and detection time by up to 85% while incurring less than an 8% drop in F1 score. These results highlight the potential of the adapted DQN model selection strategy to enable efficient, low-latency anomaly detection in resource-constrained edge cloud environments.

1. Introduction

Web application services and networks face significant risks, including ongoing exposure to security threats and performance issues, presenting a range of anomalies. These anomalies can cause severe consequences such as data breaches, service disruptions, and compromised user experiences [1,2]. Therefore, it is crucial to employ effective anomaly detection mechanisms to identify and mitigate these unexpected patterns in real-time.

Traditional anomaly detection approaches typically rely on statistical analysis or machine learning techniques applied to centralized cloud environments. However, with the advent of edge computing, where computational resources are distributed closer to the network edge, there is a growing need for anomaly detection solutions designed specifically for edge cloud environments. Edge clouds offer the advantage of reduced latency and improved response times by processing data closer to the source. However, they often operate under resource constraints, making anomaly detection a challenging task that requires accurate resource management and optimization.

In this paper, we propose a model selection approach for resource efficient anomaly detection in edge clouds through the utilization and adaptation of deep reinforcement learning. Deep reinforcement learning has shown promise in optimizing complex systems through trial-

and-error learning and decision-making based on rewards. Specifically, we employ an adapted Deep Q-Network (DQN) [3], a powerful deep reinforcement learning technique, to train an agent that dynamically selects and switches among pre-trained anomaly detection models based on available resources, detection latency, and accuracy requirements.

Our primary goal is to minimize computational resource requirements for anomaly detection while reducing the detection time and achieving a reasonable detection accuracy through adaptive selection of the anomaly detection models based on the system's status.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Proposal of a model selection approach for resource-efficient anomaly detection in edge clouds using an adapted Deep Q-Network (DQN). The method enables dynamic switching between detection models based on observed system conditions, optimizing for accuracy, latency, and resource usage.
- Development of a realistic edge-cloud testbed that integrates reinforcement learning with multiple anomaly detection models. The testbed supports controlled anomaly injection, real-time monitoring, and deployment of learning agents, enabling systematic experimentation in a reproducible environment.

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- Extensive experimental evaluation across two representative anomaly scenarios, namely, VSI-DDoS and combined anomalies, demonstrating the effectiveness of the proposed approach under real-world edge constraints.
- In-depth ablation study isolating the impact of key design elements, including the reward function, state representation, and exploration settings. This analysis highlights the individual contributions of each component to the overall system performance.

2. Related work

There are a few works done in the area of resource optimization for edge clouds. Notably, Chen et al. [4] investigate the problem of the monetary cost minimization in mobile-edge computing (MEC) system in a cooperative scenario. Accordingly, they propose an online dynamic computation offloading algorithm that correctly decides the local execution and computation offloading policy. The simulation results verify the theoretical analysis, and show that the proposed algorithm can balance the system cost and the queue length of the system. He et al. [5] address the Edge User Allocation (EUA) problem with two optimization goals. First, maximize the number of allocated users and. Second, minimize the number of required edge servers while satisfying the proximity and capacity constraints. As a result, they use the Lexicographic Goal Programming (LGP) technique to solve the EUA problem. Multiple optimization objectives are ranked by their levels of importance, or priorities, using the LGP technique. The problem solver attempt to find an optimal solution that meets the primary objective before moving on to the next objective without compromising the previous one(s).

Moreover, Duc et al. [6] provide a comprehensive survey of machine learning methods for reliable resource provisioning in edge-cloud computing. The authors explore various techniques and approaches utilized to address the challenges of resource allocation, load balancing, and performance optimization in the context of edge computing and cloud environments. The survey covers a wide range of topics, including resource prediction, task scheduling, energy efficiency, and fault tolerance. The paper serves as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners seeking to understand the current landscape of machine learning solutions for resource provisioning in edge-cloud computing systems.

Moving to UAV-enabled edge-cloud systems, Mei et al. [7] focus on joint trajectory-resource optimization in a UAV-enabled edge-cloud system with virtualized mobile clone. The authors propose a novel approach that integrates UAV trajectory planning and resource allocation to optimize the performance of edge-cloud systems. By leveraging virtualized mobile clone technology, the system aims to enhance resource utilization, reduce latency, and improve energy efficiency. The paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the proposed approach, including system architecture, mathematical formulation, and optimization algorithms. The findings highlight the potential of joint trajectory-resource optimization in UAV-enabled edge-cloud systems, offering insights for future research and development in this domain.

Finally, Li et al. [8] address the optimization of financial cost and user experience in edge cloud computing systems through a resource and replica management strategy. The authors propose a comprehensive framework that considers the trade-off between financial cost and user experience by dynamically adjusting resource allocation and replica placement. The strategy aims to minimize the operational cost of edge cloud systems while ensuring high-quality user experiences. The paper provides a detailed analysis of the proposed approach, including the formulation of optimization models and the design of algorithms. The findings highlight the effectiveness of the resource and replica management strategy in achieving cost optimization and improved user satisfaction in edge cloud computing systems, offering valuable insights for the development of efficient resource management techniques in this domain.

While several studies have investigated resource optimization and anomaly detection within edge clouds separately, there is a notable gap

Fig. 1. A general architecture of edge clouds [16].

in the existing literature. Specifically, To the best of the author's knowledge, no prior work has addressed the challenge of resource efficiency for anomaly detection in the context of edge clouds.

3. Background

This section presents a concise overview of the key concepts related to the proposed approach.

3.1. Edge clouds

Edge clouds [9] represent a paradigm shift in decentralized computing, fundamentally aiming to bridge the gap between data generation and processing. By distributing computational resources to the network periphery, edge clouds significantly reduce latency and enhance real-time processing capabilities. This spatial proximity enables edge clouds to facilitate real-time data processing and analysis, which is crucial for latency-sensitive applications. Key use cases include autonomous transportation [10,11], smart healthcare [12,13], and augmented reality [14,15]. A general architecture of edge clouds is presented in Fig. 1.

3.2. Anomaly detection

Anomaly detection [17] plays a crucial role in data analysis and system monitoring, especially within complex distributed environments such as edge clouds. The primary objective of anomaly detection is to identify patterns or occurrences exhibiting significant deviations from the established norm within a given dataset. This capability is fundamental for protecting the security and reliability of complex distributed infrastructures, including edge clouds, where promptly identifying anomalies is paramount. These anomalies encompass a broad range of issues, including security threats, hardware malfunctions, or abnormal user activities [18]. One of the main challenges in anomaly detection for edge clouds arises from resource constraints, which necessitates innovative and resource-efficient anomaly detection techniques that dynamically adjust computational complexity based on system demands.

3.3. Reinforcement learning

Reinforcement learning (RL) [19] is a branch of machine learning that addresses the challenge of decision-making in dynamic and uncertain environments. Unlike supervised learning, RL enables agents to interact with an environment and optimize decision-making through trial and error, making it particularly effective for autonomous systems.

The reinforcement learning process typically involves the following components:

- **The agent:** This is the decision-making entity that interacts with the environment. The agent takes actions based on its current state and receives feedback in the form of rewards or penalties.
- **The environment:** This is the external system that the agent interacts with. It could be a physical environment, a simulated environment, or a software application.
- **Actions:** These are the decisions taken by the agent in response to the feedback from the environment. The agent chooses actions based on its current state and the expected rewards associated with each action. Actions may include switching between anomaly detection models, tuning model hyperparameters, or reallocating system resources dynamically.
- **State:** This is the current condition of the agent and the environment. It includes all relevant information that the agent can use to make decisions. The proposed approach defines the system state based on three critical parameters: resource usage, detection time, and F1 score. These metrics effectively capture the trade-offs between computational efficiency and anomaly detection performance in resource-constrained edge cloud environments.
- **Rewards:** These are the feedback signals that the agent receives from the environment. In our DQN-based approach, the reward function is designed to balance detection accuracy, detection latency, and computational cost. Specifically, it combines normalized measures of F1 score, resource usage, and detection time into a single scalar signal that guides the agent toward selecting models that achieve high detection quality with minimal resource overhead.

3.4. Q-learning and deep Q-network (DQN)

Q-learning [20] is a model-free reinforcement learning algorithm that learns an optimal policy by estimating the maximum expected future reward for each possible action from a given state. It is suited to problems in which an agent must learn from trial and error in an unknown environment.

The Q-learning algorithm is based on the concept of a Q-function, which maps state-action pairs to their corresponding expected future rewards. The Q-function, denoted by $Q(s, a)$, represents the expected reward for taking action a in state s , and it is updated iteratively during learning. The goal is to approximate the optimal Q-function, $Q^*(s, a)$, which yields the maximum expected future reward for each state-action pair.

Q-learning follows the Bellman equation [21], which decomposes the expected future reward into immediate reward and the discounted optimal future reward. The update rule is:

$$Q(s, a) \leftarrow Q(s, a) + \alpha [r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a') - Q(s, a)] \quad (1)$$

where r is the immediate reward for taking action a in state s , s' is the next state, α is the learning rate, and γ is the discount factor. The term $\max_{a'} Q(s', a')$ represents the maximum expected future reward from state s' .

At each iteration, the agent selects actions using an exploration-exploitation strategy such as epsilon-greedy [22], balancing exploration of new actions with exploitation of the current best-known action.

While Q-learning uses a tabular representation of the Q-function, Deep Q-Networks (DQN) [3] extend this approach by using a deep neural network to approximate $Q(s, a; \theta)$, where θ are the network parameters. DQN introduces two key enhancements:

- **Experience Replay:** Transitions (s, a, r, s') are stored in a replay buffer and sampled randomly to break correlation between updates.
- **Target Network:** A separate target network with parameters θ^- is used to compute the target $r + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s', a'; \theta^-)$, and is updated periodically to stabilize learning.

Although pure Q-learning is computationally lightweight and highly interpretable, DQN offers greater representational power for high-dimensional state spaces. In this work, we compare both approaches and demonstrate that the adapted DQN achieves the best trade-off between resource efficiency and detection performance in our edge anomaly detection scenarios.

3.5. Symbols and notations

We provide a summary of the key symbols and notations used throughout this paper in Table 1. These notations are primarily related to resource usage, anomaly detection performance metrics, and the reinforcement learning-based model selection process.

4. System model

In this section, we introduce our proposed model selection approach for resource efficient anomaly detection in edge clouds, as shown in Fig. 2, and present the resource optimization problem associated with this matter.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the proposed approach along with the testbed: a ModelMesh agent automatically optimizes between three main parameters including relative F1-measure, model’s resource usage, and model’s detection time, to select the most efficient setup for anomaly detection.

Table 1
Summary of Symbols and Notations.

Symbol	Description
S	Set of edge servers
$R_s(t)$	Resource usage in server s at time t
F_i	Relative F1-measure of anomaly detection model i
DT_i	Detection time of anomaly detection model i
R_{\max}	Maximum allowable resource usage in edge servers
F_{\min}	Minimum acceptable F1-measure for anomaly detection
DT_{\max}	Maximum allowable detection time
s_t	System state at time t
a_t	Action taken at time t (selected model)
r_t	Reward at time t
α	Learning rate in Q-learning or DQN
γ	Discount factor in Q-learning or DQN
ϵ	Epsilon (exploration-exploitation parameter) in ϵ -greedy policy
$Q(s, a)$	Q-value for state s and action a (tabular Q-learning)
$Q(s, a; \theta)$	Q-value approximated by the neural network in DQN with parameters θ
$\max_{a'} Q(s', a')$	Maximum Q-value for the next state
θ	Parameters of the Q-network in DQN
θ^-	Parameters of the target network in DQN
Replay Buffer	Memory storing past transitions (s, a, r, s') for DQN training
$\pi(s)$	Policy mapping states to actions

4.1. Efficient anomaly detection leveraging deep Q-networks

In this paper, edge clouds includes a network of edge servers, end-users, and a container-based microservice application designed to meet diverse user demands. In this environment, we use anomaly injectors to create anomalies for a thorough system evaluation. The process of anomaly detection follows a step-by-step approach:

1. The application initiates interactions, responding to user requests for various services.
2. Simultaneously, anomalies are injected and allowed to emerge within the system.
3. A monitoring module collects crucial system data, essential for a comprehensive evaluation of the system's status.
4. Subsequently, the detection module receives the information collected by the monitoring module and classifies the system's status as either normal or anomalous.

Within this edge cloud environment, optimizing the resource usage of anomaly detection models is essential for efficient anomaly detection and edge cloud operations. Considering an anomaly detection model running on an edge server consumes critical edge resources, we formulate this as an optimization problem: minimize resource usage while adhering to specified accuracy and detection time constraints.

We define the following variables:

- S : Set of edge servers
- $R_s(t)$: Resource usage in server s at time t
- F_i : Relative F1-measure of anomaly detection model i
- DT_i : Detection time of anomaly detection model i
- R_{\max} : Maximum allowable resource usage in edge servers
- F_{\min} : Minimum acceptable F1-measure of the anomaly detector
- DT_{\max} : Maximum allowable detection time of the anomaly detector

The objective is to minimize resource usage while ensuring a certain level of accuracy and detection time. We formulate the problem as follows:

$$\text{Minimize: } \sum_{s \in S} R_s(t)$$

$$\text{Subject to: } R_s(t) \leq R_{\max}$$

$$F_i \geq F_{\min}$$

$$DT_i \leq DT_{\max}$$

To ensure computational efficiency and real-time adaptability, our adapted Deep Q-Network (DQN) agent uses a compact yet informative state representation. The state space is defined using three key parameters: resource usage, detection time, and F1 score. These parameters directly capture the trade-offs between computational efficiency and detection performance. While additional metrics such as network latency or memory usage could improve granularity, they would enlarge the state space and slow convergence, which are unacceptable in time-sensitive edge scenarios. By keeping the state representation lightweight, our approach maintains rapid decision-making without excessive overhead.

The proposed DQN approach optimizes anomaly detection efficiency by using a neural network to approximate the action-value function, $Q(s, a; \theta)$, and dynamically selecting the most suitable detection model. Although one could extend the action space to include hyperparameter tuning or dynamic resource allocation, doing so would greatly increase computational cost and decision latency. Instead, we employ a finite set of pre-trained detection models, each tailored to different accuracy, resource, and latency trade-offs. The DQN agent, trained via experience replay and a target network, learns to select among these models in real time, achieving rapid adaptation with minimal additional cost.

4.2. Proposed approach

In this section we explain the proposed approach which consists of three components as follows:

- **Sampling:** In this component, first we take a history window of the last 500 monitored records of the system status as R_t . Afterwards, we select 200 random samples from R_t and call it S_t . This component is presented in [Algorithm 1](#). The use of random sampling ensures that the DQN agent is exposed to diverse system conditions, improving its ability to generalize across different anomaly scenarios. Model stability is maintained as the learning process iterates over multiple episodes, and the experience replay buffer further mitigates sample bias. While stratified sampling could ensure proportional representation of different system states, our empirical evaluations show that uniform random sampling suffices, with learning remaining consistent across independent runs.
- **State identification:** In this component, as presented in [Algorithm 1](#), first we perform classification with the best static model for records in S_t and call it BC_t . Second, we take the classification done by the selected model for the same records in S_t and call it SC_t . Then we calculate the relative F1 measure for the selected model based on BC_t and SC_t and call it F_t . We then pass F_t , system resource usage, and selected model's detection time to the

Algorithm 1: Optimization Process for Model Selection.

Input : R_t : monitored system records,

BM_t : best static anomaly detection model

Output: SM_{t+1} : model selected by the learning agent
 $i \leftarrow 0$;

while True do

 Retrieve last 500 records: R_t ;

 Randomly sample 200 entries from R_t : S_t ;

 Perform classification on S_t using best model:

$BC_t \leftarrow \text{Classification}(S_t, BM_t)$;

 Perform classification on S_t using selected model:

$SC_t \leftarrow \text{Classification}(S_t, SM_t)$;

 Compute relative F1 score: $F_t \leftarrow \text{RelativeF1}(BC_t, SC_t)$;

 Query agent for updated model:

$SM_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{Algorithm 2}(F_t, \text{CPU}, \text{DT})$;

 Wait for the next 1000 records to arrive;

$i \leftarrow i + 1$;

DQN agent. We have defined four states, namely, *Severe*, *VeryBad*, *Bad*, and *Good*, as shown in Table 3.

- **Adapted Deep Q-Network agent:** We selected Deep Q-Network (DQN) as the reinforcement learning algorithm for model selection due to its balance between learning capacity and computational overhead. While policy-gradient methods such as Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) or Asynchronous Advantage Actor-Critic (A3C) can provide performance benefits in complex and high-dimensional environments, they typically require extensive tuning and heavier runtime costs. In contrast, DQN is particularly well-suited to problems with relatively small and structured state spaces, such as our edge anomaly detection setup, where system states are defined by CPU usage, detection latency, and detection quality. Moreover, DQN supports experience replay and target network stabilization, which improve learning convergence without introducing significant architectural complexity. This makes it ideal for resource-constrained edge environments where lightweight adaptability and real-time responsiveness are critical. Let s_t be the state vector at time t , containing resource usage, detection time, and relative F1 score. Let $a_t \in \mathcal{A}$ be the action, i.e., the choice of anomaly detection model. The DQN agent approximates the action-value function $Q(s, a; \theta)$ with parameters θ , and maintains a target network $Q(s, a; \theta^-)$ for stability.

- (1) Observe transition (s_t, a_t, r_t, s_{t+1}) , where $r_t = f(R_t, DT_t, F_t)$ balances CPU usage, latency, and F1. The reward function is computed as a weighted combination of the normalized CPU usage, detection time, and relative F1 score. CPU and detection time are normalized against their respective upper thresholds, and the relative F1 score is scaled to the $[0, 1]$ range. The weights in our experiments are $w_1 = 0.33$, $w_2 = 0.33$, and $w_3 = 0.34$, which reflect an approximately equal emphasis on computational efficiency and detection quality.
- (2) Store the transition in replay buffer D .
- (3) Sample a minibatch from D , compute targets $y_i = r_i + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s'_i, a'; \theta^-)$, and update θ via gradient descent on

$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_i (Q(s_i, a_i; \theta) - y_i)^2.$$
- (4) Periodically sync $\theta^- \leftarrow \theta$.
- (5) Select the next action via ϵ -greedy: with probability ϵ choose random a , otherwise $a = \arg \max_{a'} Q(s_{t+1}, a'; \theta)$.

The full algorithm is given in Algorithm 2.

Training protocol and convergence criteria. For each (ϵ, γ) configuration, we train the DQN agent for six episodes, where each episode sequentially processes the entire training portion of the dataset. The environment advances in non-overlapping blocks of 500 records; within each block, the agent samples 200 records at random, computes the reward, updates Q , and proceeds to the next block.

The Q-network employs a learning rate of 10^{-3} , a replay buffer of 20 000 transitions, a minibatch size of 128, and a target network that is synchronized every 500 gradient steps. Training terminates early if the mean absolute change in Q-values across episodes drops below 10^{-3} for three consecutive episodes, or continues until the sixth episode is completed. A full summary of the fixed hyperparameters used throughout our experiments is provided in Table 2.

To promote convergence in practice, our implementation adopts two stabilizing techniques originally introduced in the DQN framework, namely, experience replay and a separate target network, which are now widely used in the deep reinforcement learning literature [23]. Recent theoretical studies have further supported the convergence behavior of DQN under practical conditions [24–26]. These works demonstrate that, under certain assumptions, DQN can achieve provable convergence and bounded sample complexity even when using ϵ -greedy exploration.

Table 2

Fixed hyper-parameters used for all DQN experiments.

Parameter	Value
Episodes per configuration	6
Block size (<i>history_window</i>)	500 records
Samples per decision	200 records
Discount factor γ	{0.70, 0.80, 0.90}
Exploration rate ϵ	{0.05, 0.10, 0.15}
ϵ_{\min} / decay	0.05 / 0.995
Learning rate (Adam)	1×10^{-3}
Replay-buffer size	20 000 transitions
Minibatch size	128
Target-network update frequency	500 steps
Optimiser	Adam

Table 3

Different states of the system.

State	R	DT	$F1$
Severe	High	High	Low
VeryBad	High	Low	Low
	Low	High	Low
Bad	Low	Low	Low
	High	High	High
	High	Low	High
Good	Low	Low	High

Across all experiments, we observed smooth and stable convergence of the empirical return curves without divergence or oscillation.

5. Experimental evaluation

In this section, our evaluation focuses on analyzing the system's behaviour, both before and after applying the proposed approach. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the system's performance, we implemented a testbed setup and employed a monitoring framework to observe the system's behavior across different scenarios. Furthermore, we present the results obtained from our experiments and conduct a thorough analysis of the proposed approach under various experimental scenarios. Through these evaluations, we aim to assess the effectiveness of the approach in optimizing resource consumption and improving overall anomaly detection efficiency. Additionally, we provide a comprehensive analysis of the experimental results to identify any potential trade-offs or limitations associated with the approach, ultimately providing a comprehensive assessment of its feasibility across different scenarios.

5.1. Testbed setup and monitoring

We conducted an extensive evaluation of the system's behavior both before and after applying the proposed approach. For this purpose, we deployed a container-based microservice application, *Sock Shop*,¹ on an edge cloud environment composed of multiple edge servers orchestrated using Kubernetes.² Each edge server is equipped with an Intel Core i7-8700 3.20 GHz CPU and 32 GB of RAM. This setup enables controlled anomaly injection and fine-grained monitoring while reflecting key characteristics of real-world edge cloud deployments.

An overview of the experimental testbed architecture is also provided in Fig. 3, which illustrates the layered structure of the system, including the anomaly injector, application stack, and anomaly detection module.

¹ <https://microservices-demo.github.io/>

² <https://kubernetes.io/>

Fig. 3. Overview of the experimental testbed used in this study.

Algorithm 2: Adapted Deep Q Network (DQN) for Anomaly Detection Model Selection.

Input : ϵ : exploration rate for ϵ -greedy action selection,
 γ : discount factor controlling future reward impact,
 lr : learning rate for Q-network optimization,
 c : current CPU usage of the system,
 t : detection time of the current model,
 f : relative F1 score of the selected model,
 D : replay buffer storing past experience tuples,
 N : minibatch size for training,
 θ : parameters of the Q-network,
 θ^- : parameters of the target Q-network,
 C : frequency of updating the target network

Output: Selected model SM

```

if initial_state then
    Initialize current state  $s \leftarrow (c, t, f)$ ;
    Randomly select an action  $a \in \mathcal{A}$ ;
     $SM \leftarrow a$  (select model associated with action  $a$ );
else
    Observe new state  $s' \leftarrow (c, t, f)$ ;
    Store transition  $(s, a, r, s')$  in replay buffer  $D$ ;
    Sample minibatch  $\{(s_i, a_i, r_i, s'_i)\}_{i=1}^N$  from  $D$ ;
    for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
        Compute target value:  $y_i \leftarrow r_i + \gamma \max_{a'} Q(s'_i, a'; \theta^-)$ ;
    Update Q-network by minimizing loss:
        
$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (Q(s_i, a_i; \theta) - y_i)^2$$

    if current_step mod  $C = 0$  then
        Update target network:  $\theta^- \leftarrow \theta$ ;
    Select new action  $a$  using  $\epsilon$ -greedy strategy on  $Q(s', :, \theta)$ ;
    Set  $SM \leftarrow a$ , and update current state  $s \leftarrow s'$ ;
    
```

For the evaluation, we defined two distinct scenarios to assess the effectiveness of the proposed approach:

- **Scenario-I: VSI-DDoS on edge clouds:** This scenario focused on evaluating the proposed model selection approach for resource-efficient anomaly detection in the context of a low-rate Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attack known as Very Short Intermittent DDoS (VSI-DDoS), specifically targeting the edge clouds. Unlike tra-

ditional DDoS attacks characterized by high volumes of traffic, VSI-DDoS attacks are more subtle and low-rate, making them particularly challenging to detect using conventional methods [16]. By introducing VSI-DDoS attacks, we aimed to examine the effectiveness of our approach in detecting and mitigating these low-rate DDoS anomalies, thus protecting the edge clouds from disruptive attacks. In VSI-DDoS attack configuration, we implemented 10 synchronized attacker nodes using Apache Benchmark, each sending bursts of HTTP requests at predefined intervals. On average, attack bursts were generated every 75ms, with each burst containing approximately 3000 requests. An idle interval (Δ) of 2 seconds was maintained between bursts to consider the intermittent nature of VSI-DDoS.

- **Scenario-II: Combined anomalies on edge clouds:** This scenario aimed to validate the proposed model selection approach for resource-efficient anomaly detection in a comprehensive manner. We considered the occurrence of both security and performance anomalies simultaneously on the edge clouds. The objective is to thoroughly evaluate the effectiveness of the approach by designing a series of experiments that introduced various types of security and performance anomalies. By assessing the system's response to these combined anomalies, we determine the approach's ability to efficiently detect and handle multiple anomalous situations in the edge cloud environment. Security-based anomalies were generated using *SlowHTTPTest*,³ which introduced multiple types of low-rate denial-of-service (DoS) attacks, including *Slow Headers (Slowloris)*, *Slow Body (R-U-Dead-Yet)*, *Range Attacks (Apache Killer)*, and *Slow Read Attacks*. These attacks were crafted to slowly deplete server resources by keeping connections open for prolonged periods, making detection challenging. In addition, performance anomalies were injected using *stress-ng*,⁴ which applied extreme workloads to edge servers. The CPU-intensive workload maintained high CPU consumption over an extended period, while memory-intensive operations forced rapid memory consumption to induce system degradation. These conditions aimed to show real-world performance bottlenecks under high system loads.

The selection of these two scenarios is based on their ability to represent real-world challenges encountered in edge cloud anomaly detection:

- **Diversity of Anomalies:** The chosen scenarios include both network-based threats (VSI-DDoS) and multi-faceted system disrup-

³ <https://www.kali.org/tools/slowhttptest/>

⁴ <https://wiki.ubuntu.com/Kernel/Reference/stress-ng>

tions (Combined Anomalies), ensuring coverage of both security and performance-related incidents.

- **Practical Relevance:** VSI-DDoS attacks are particularly difficult to detect due to their intermittent nature, making them a critical test case. Meanwhile, Combined Anomalies reflect complex operational environments where multiple issues occur simultaneously, testing the robustness of our model in handling real-world edge cloud conditions.
- **Computational Trade-offs:** These scenarios effectively highlight the trade-offs between detection performance and resource efficiency, which are central to our study.

We conducted comprehensive monitoring on three layers of the testbed setup: the application-layer, virtualization-layer, and physical-layer. At the application-layer, we collected crucial metrics such as the number of requests per second, the number of failed requests per second, and the total number of failed requests related to the deployed target application. For virtualization-layer monitoring, we gathered service-related metrics, including CPU usage, memory utilization, and network activity of the containers associated with the three key services under examination: “Catalogue”, “Carts”, and “Front-end”. Finally, in the physical-layer monitoring, we collected metrics related to the edge servers themselves. This included monitoring CPU usage, memory consumption, and network usage of all the edge servers.

5.2. Results and analysis

The detection models were implemented using the Keras⁵ library with the TensorFlow⁶ backend. We performed a grid search over the exploration rate ϵ and discount factor γ to tune the DQN agent. Each configuration was evaluated on cumulative reward, which integrates CPU usage, detection time, and relative F1; higher reward indicates a more favorable trade-off. Prior to training, raw metrics were min-max normalized to [0, 1]. To reduce dimensionality and focus the agent and models on key system behaviors, we retained only the most informative features such as overall CPU utilization, requests per second, failed requests per second, and median response time, and imputed any missing values in these columns with the feature mean prior to training.

To evaluate the effectiveness of our adaptive DQN-based model selection approach, we compare its performance against three baselines: (i) the *best static model*, which always selects the most accurate detector and achieves a perfect F1 score of 1.00 at the cost of high computational overhead; (ii) a *random agent*, which selects among the available models uniformly at random without any optimization strategy; and (iii) a *tabular Q-learning agent*, which relies on a discrete state-action table without function approximation.

Table 4 presents the results for Scenario I (VSI-DDoS). Among the evaluated configurations, $(\epsilon, \gamma) = (0.05, 0.70)$ yields the highest cumulative reward of 0.6026, with a CPU usage of 80.67%, detection latency of 10.30 μs , and a relative F1 score of 0.924. When compared to the best static detector configuration, which operates at 90.78% CPU usage, 69 μs latency, and an F1 score of 1.00, this setting achieves a 10.11% reduction in CPU usage and an 85.1% reduction in latency, while incurring only a 7.6% decrease in F1 score.

The complete set of training and evaluation curves across the (ϵ, γ) grid for both scenarios is provided in Appendix A. Fig. 4a shows that under the configuration $(\epsilon, \gamma) = (0.05, 0.70)$, the DQN agent consistently converges to a lightweight detection model. This results in sustained low CPU usage while maintaining a high relative F1 score. Increasing the discount factor to $\gamma = 0.80$ leads to a modest rise in CPU usage to 80.91% and detection latency to 11.10 μs , while the F1 score drops only slightly to 0.917 (see Appendix A, Fig. A.1). Further increasing γ to 0.90 results in higher CPU usage (84.69%) and latency (21.80 μs),

Fig. 4. Scenario-I, best hyper-parameter pair ($\epsilon=0.05, \gamma=0.7$): (a) training model-selection behavior; (b) post-training evaluation performance. The full (ϵ, γ) grid is shown in Appendix A. The vertical striping pattern with different colors at the bottom of each plot indicates the agent’s switching behavior between different anomaly detection models over time.

⁵ <https://keras.io/>

⁶ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

Table 4

Scenario-I: DQN performance over the (ϵ, γ) grid, plus a Random baseline and the Best static model.

ϵ	γ	CPU	Det. Time (μ s)	Rel. F1	Reward
0.05	0.7	80.67	10.30	0.924	0.6026
0.05	0.8	80.91	11.10	0.917	0.5882
0.05	0.9	84.69	21.80	0.927	0.4955
0.10	0.7	81.17	11.80	0.919	0.5840
0.10	0.8	81.13	11.60	0.923	0.5895
0.10	0.9	81.34	12.30	0.923	0.5807
0.15	0.7	81.80	13.60	0.923	0.5697
0.15	0.8	81.64	12.90	0.914	0.5708
0.15	0.9	81.42	12.30	0.922	0.5823
Random agent		88.92	33.50	0.9211	0.3727
Best static model		90.78	69.00	1.00	-

Table 5

Scenario-II: DQN performance over the (ϵ, γ) grid, plus a Random baseline and the Best static model.

ϵ	γ	CPU	Det. Time (μ s)	Rel. F1	Reward
0.05	0.7	9.06	12.00	0.705	0.4537
0.05	0.8	9.81	14.70	0.748	0.4626
0.05	0.9	13.41	24.60	0.790	0.3734
0.10	0.7	13.26	24.60	0.784	0.3669
0.10	0.8	10.25	15.80	0.734	0.4368
0.10	0.9	13.58	24.80	0.796	0.3617
0.15	0.7	12.92	23.20	0.736	0.3438
0.15	0.8	13.56	25.00	0.762	0.3354
0.15	0.9	10.50	16.00	0.741	0.4374
Random agent		16.17	30.80	0.7930	0.3110
Best static model		18.05	69.00	1.00	-

with only a marginal F1 recovery to 0.927 and a reduced reward of 0.4955.

When ϵ increases to 0.10, the agent adopts a more exploratory behavior, leading to slightly higher CPU usage (81.13–81.34%) and latency (11.60–12.30 μ s), while achieving a modest improvement in relative F1 (0.923). The highest reward within this configuration set is obtained at (0.10, 0.80) with a value of 0.5895, suggesting that moderate exploration coupled with balanced consideration of future rewards yields robust performance. In contrast, at $\epsilon = 0.15$, exploration becomes excessive: CPU usage increases further to 81.42–81.80%, latency rises to 12.30–13.60 μ s, and F1 exhibits more fluctuation (0.914–0.923), with the highest reward reaching only 0.5708. These trends are visualized in Appendix A, Figs. A.1 and A.2. For comparison, the random agent baseline (88.92% CPU, 33.50 μ s, F1 = 0.9211, reward = 0.3727), the best static model (90.78% CPU, 69 μ s, F1 = 1.00), and the tabular Q-learning agent all perform considerably worse in terms of reward, underscoring the advantage of adaptive DQN strategies.

Table 5 summarizes the results for Scenario II, which involves both security-related and performance-related anomalies. The best-performing configuration is $(\epsilon, \gamma) = (0.05, 0.80)$, achieving a reward of 0.4626 with CPU usage at 9.81%, detection latency of 14.70 μ s, and a relative F1 score of 0.748. Compared to the best static model (18.05% CPU, 69 μ s latency, F1 = 1.00), this setting reduces CPU consumption by 45.7% and latency by 78.7%, with a trade-off of a 25.2% decrease in detection accuracy. As illustrated in Appendix A, Fig. A.3, the agent under this configuration is able to adapt effectively to both denial-of-service and resource exhaustion anomalies, consistently favoring lightweight models during extended periods of system stress. At (0.05, 0.70), the agent minimizes CPU to 9.06% but the F1 drops to 0.705 (reward 0.4537), whereas at (0.05, 0.90) the F1 recovers to 0.790, but CPU usage increases to 13.41%. Similar trade-offs are observed in the $\epsilon = 0.10$ and 0.15 configurations, where increased exploration occasionally yields marginal F1 gains but leads to elevated CPU and latency, resulting in overall lower reward values compared to the (0.05, 0.80) policy. these

results show that the random agent baseline (16.17% CPU, 30.80 μ s latency, F1 = 0.7930, reward = 0.3110), the best static model, and the tabular Q-learning agent are all consistently outperformed by every DQN-based configurations.

Across both scenarios, the DQN agent demonstrates a strong ability to navigate the inherent trade-offs between resource consumption, detection latency, and accuracy. When configured with $(\epsilon, \gamma) = (0.05, 0.70 - 0.80)$, the agent consistently achieves substantial reductions in CPU usage (10–46%) and detection latency (78–85%) relative to the best static model, while keeping the decline in relative F1 score within acceptable bounds—under 8% in Scenario I and under 25% in Scenario II. These results underscore the effectiveness of DQN-based model selection in enabling efficient, real-time anomaly detection within resource-constrained edge cloud environments (Fig. 4).

5.3. Ablation studies

To quantify the individual contributions of the reward function and state space design in our proposed approach, we retrain and evaluate both tabular Q-learning and DQN agents under five ablated environment configurations:

- **BASE**: Original reward function and full state representation.
- **R-CPU**: CPU usage penalty removed from the reward function.
- **R weights**: Reward function reweighted to prioritize F1 (weights = 0.1 CPU, 0.1 DT, 0.8 F1).
- **STATE-CPU**: CPU usage removed from the input state representation.
- **R&STATE-CPU**: CPU usage removed from both the reward and the state.

Tables 6 and 7 summarize the results, reporting average reward, CPU usage, detection time (μ s), and relative F1-score for each configuration across both test scenarios.

Tabular Q-learning Behavior. As shown in Table 6, the tabular Q-learning agent exhibits strong sensitivity to the presence of CPU cost in the reward and state:

- In Scenario-I, removing CPU from the reward (**R-CPU**) or the state (**STATE-CPU**) causes the agent to consistently favor the fastest available models. This reduces detection latency by approximately 71% (from 40.9 to 11.8 μ s), but also leads to a drop in F1-score (from 0.924 to 0.883).
- The **R&STATE-CPU** configuration produces behavior nearly identical to **R-CPU**, confirming that excluding CPU from either the state or reward is sufficient to push the policy toward low-latency, high-efficiency models, regardless of detection quality.
- The **R weights** variant, which heavily prioritizes F1 in the reward, leads to improved detection accuracy (up to 0.967 in Scenario-II) but increases both CPU usage and latency.

DQN Behavior. Table 7 illustrates that the DQN agent is more robust to these ablations due to its function approximation and capacity for generalization:

- The **STATE-CPU** variant (removing CPU from the input state) has negligible impact. The DQN agent maintains behavior similar to the **BASE** configuration, with CPU, latency, and F1 all within 1%.
- When CPU is removed from the reward (**R-CPU**), there is only a modest shift toward faster models (e.g., detection time drops by 1.5 μ s), with negligible loss in F1.
- The **R&STATE-CPU** variant produces results nearly identical to **R-CPU**, indicating that as long as CPU cost is captured in the reward, the agent learns to avoid high-cost models, even without CPU visibility in the state.

Table 6

Ablation results for the tabular Q-learning agent.

Tabular Q-Learning				
Variant	Reward	CPU	DT (μ s)	F1
Scenario-I				
BASE	0.538	81.99	40.9	0.924
R-CPU	0.824	80.78	11.8	0.883
R weights	0.775	81.62	31.4	0.885
STATE-CPU	0.546	80.78	11.8	0.883
R&STATE-CPU	0.778	81.62	33.1	0.885
Scenario-II				
BASE	0.422	12.02	20.4	0.718
R-CPU	0.635	8.41	9.2	0.453
R weights	0.816	17.68	35.6	0.967
STATE-CPU	0.334	8.42	9.2	0.455
R&STATE-CPU	0.637	8.41	9.0	0.454

Table 7

Ablation results for the DQN agent.

DQN				
Variant	Reward	CPU	DT (μ s)	F1
Scenario-I				
BASE	0.536	81.15	20.0	0.883
R-CPU	0.809	81.15	19.7	0.884
R weights	0.802	82.26	45.3	0.921
STATE-CPU	0.537	81.14	19.2	0.884
R&STATE-CPU	0.812	81.14	19.1	0.884
Scenario-II				
BASE	0.415	13.53	28.1	0.773
R-CPU	0.604	8.81	12.6	0.461
R weights	0.802	17.59	35.1	0.948
STATE-CPU	0.415	13.53	28.1	0.772
R&STATE-CPU	0.627	8.82	10.4	0.462

- As with tabular Q-learning, the **R weights** configuration increases accuracy (F1 up to 0.948) at the expense of higher CPU usage and longer detection time.

5.4. Discussion and limitations

The analysis of both Scenario-I and Scenario-II highlights the effectiveness of the proposed DQN-based model selection framework in dynamically adapting to system conditions in edge cloud environments. The agent learns to balance detection quality with resource constraints by tuning the exploration-exploitation trade-off (via ϵ), the discounting of future rewards (via γ), and leveraging stability techniques such as experience replay and a target network. These findings underscore the importance of hyperparameter tuning to align system behavior with application-specific anomaly detection requirements.

Experimental results confirm that the proposed approach can significantly reduce resource consumption and detection latency, making it a strong candidate for real-time anomaly detection at the edge. However, we also observe a trade-off: although the F1-score remains high, it does exhibit a modest reduction in favor of resource savings. This trade-off is domain-dependent. For instance:

- **Security-Critical Applications** (e.g., financial services, industrial control): Even small reductions in detection accuracy can increase risk, favoring more conservative model selections that consume more resources.
- **Resource-Constrained Scenarios** (e.g., IoT, mobile edge, real-time analytics): In these environments, a slight decline in accuracy is often acceptable in exchange for major gains in CPU and latency efficiency.

Our design mitigates this trade-off through three key mechanisms:

- **DQN-based Adaptation:** The agent continuously updates its policy to select models that yield optimal trade-offs based on live system feedback.
- **State-aware Learning:** The state representation incorporates CPU usage, detection time, and relative F1-score, enabling the agent to make context-aware decisions.
- **Empirical Evaluation:** The complete hyperparameter grid search (A) provides insights into how different (ϵ, γ) values influence reward and performance metrics.

Scalability and Deployment Considerations. The scalability of our approach is critical to practical adoption in distributed edge environments. We address this in the following ways:

- **Controlled Complexity:** The state space remains compact (3 dimensions), and the action space is limited to a fixed set of pre-trained models. This avoids exponential growth and supports efficient training and inference.
- **Linear Scaling:** Since our DQN agent updates only based on experience tuples (not full-state evaluation), computational cost scales linearly with the number of steps and episodes.
- **Distributed Applicability:** In large-scale deployments, each edge node can operate an independent agent. Our framework is also amenable to decentralized or federated implementations where nodes share policy updates without centralized coordination. Future work may explore federated DQN or multi-agent extensions to enhance collaborative learning.

Action Space and Learning Complexity. Currently, our agent selects among pre-trained anomaly detection models. This design offers fast decision-making without retraining base detectors. However, extending the action space to include hyperparameter tuning or dynamic resource controls (e.g., CPU frequency scaling) would increase flexibility at the cost of greater complexity. Incorporating such continuous or mixed-action spaces would require advanced RL formulations, such as actor-critic models or PPO, along with more sophisticated training stabilization.

Positioning of DQN in Edge Environments. While advanced reinforcement learning algorithms (e.g., PPO, A3C) may offer benefits in more complex environments, their higher computational and memory overheads make them less suitable for real-time edge deployments. Our choice of DQN strikes a balance between representational power and runtime efficiency. As supported by recent theoretical and empirical studies, the use of experience replay and target networks allows DQN to achieve stable learning in low-dimensional state spaces with limited samples.

Future work may investigate hierarchical reinforcement learning, which could separate model selection and resource control into different layers, or multi-agent DQN to support cooperative learning across nodes.

6. Conclusion and future work

This paper proposed a DQN-based model selection framework for resource-efficient anomaly detection in edge cloud environments. The goal was to enable adaptive switching among pre-trained anomaly detection models to minimize CPU usage and detection latency while maintaining acceptable detection accuracy. Our method incorporates a lightweight Deep Q-Network agent that operates on a compact, interpretable state space and leverages established stabilization techniques such as experience replay and target networks to ensure practical convergence.

Extensive experimental results across two representative anomaly scenarios demonstrated that the proposed approach achieves significant improvements in resource efficiency, reducing CPU usage by up to 45%

and detection latency by up to 85%, with less than an 8% degradation in F1 score. These results validate that the adaptive model selection policy effectively balances computational cost and detection performance, offering a flexible and scalable solution for resource-constrained edge cloud environments.

While our results confirm the advantages of DQN for this setting, we acknowledge the trade-off between resource optimization and maximum detection accuracy. The proposed system dynamically navigates this balance, selecting the most appropriate model for each operating context based on learned experience.

Future work will aim to further enhance the scalability, flexibility, and learning capacity of the model selection framework:

- **Scalability:** We plan to investigate decentralized and federated variants of DQN to support multi-node collaboration across distributed edge clusters.
- **Adaptability:** We will explore dynamic hyperparameter tuning and context-aware policy adjustments to optimize responsiveness to real-time system conditions.
- **Extended control:** Future extensions could expand the action space to include resource allocation parameters and model-level configurations, enabling more granular optimization.
- **Advanced RL strategies:** We intend to explore extended reinforcement learning paradigms [27] such as hierarchical reinforcement learning (HRL) [28] and multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) [29]. HRL could decompose the task into separate agents for model selection and resource control, while MARL can enable decentralized coordination among multiple edge nodes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Javad Forough: Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation, Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation; **Monowar Bhuyan:** Project administration, Validation, Methodology, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization; **Erik Elmroth:** Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Resources, Validation, Funding acquisition, Supervision.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Erik Elmroth reports financial support was provided by Wallenberg AI, Autonomous Systems and Software Program (WASP) funded by

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Appendix A. Complete Hyperparameter Grids

This appendix presents the full set of training and evaluation results for all combinations of the exploration rate ϵ and discount factor γ tested in our experiments. Each subfigure corresponds to one (ϵ, γ) pair and visualizes the model-selection behavior of the agent during either training or evaluation. These visualizations complement the quantitative results presented in Tables 4 and 5 and provide deeper insight into how different agent configurations adapt to varying anomaly scenarios.

In each training plot, we show the evolution of model choices across time, capturing how the agent learns to favor lightweight or accurate models based on system conditions. The evaluation plots, in turn, reflect the agent's post-training decision patterns when applied to unseen data. Together, these grids enable a comprehensive visual comparison of agent behavior across different reinforcement learning configurations. They also help validate the robustness of our approach by highlighting consistent model selection trends in high-reward settings.

A.1. Scenario-I: VSI-DDos on edge clouds

This section presents the complete set of training and evaluation plots for all (ϵ, γ) configurations tested under Scenario-I. Figs. A.1 and A.2 show the agent's model-selection behavior and performance trends across different hyperparameter settings.

A.2. Scenario-II: Combined anomalies on edge clouds

This section includes the full grid of training and evaluation results for Scenario-II. Figs. A.3 and A.4 visualize the effect of varying (ϵ, γ) pairs on the agent's decision-making and overall performance under combined anomaly conditions.

Fig. A.1. Scenario-I (training): model-selection behavior over the (ϵ, γ) grid.

Fig. A.2. Scenario-I (evaluation): post-training performance over the (ϵ, γ) grid.

Fig. A.3. Scenario-II (training): model-selection behavior over the (ϵ, γ) grid.

Fig. A.4. Scenario-II (evaluation): post-training performance over the (ϵ, γ) grid.

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